

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ:
ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

Researchbib Impact factor: 11.79/2023

Том 2, Выпуск 1, 31 Января

METHODOLOGICAL RECOMMENDATIONS ON TEACHING
COMPOUND SENTENCES

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada 9-sinf ona tili darsida o‘tiladigan qo‘shma gap qismlarini bog‘lovchi vositalarning semantik, sintaktik xususiyatlari hamda ularning o‘qitilishiga oid metodik tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlari: Sintaksis, qo‘shma gap, bog‘langan qo‘shma gap, bog‘lovchisiz qo‘shma gap, kesim, bog‘lovchi, yuklama.

Аннотация. В статье представлены семантические и синтаксические особенности союзов и методические рекомендации по их преподаванию на уроке родного языка в 9 классе.

Ключевые слова. Синтаксис, составное предложение, связное составное предложение, составное предложение без соединительного, отрезка, связного, нагрузки.

Abstract. The article presents the semantic and syntactic features of conjunctions and methodological recommendations for their teaching in the native language lesson in the 9th grade.

Keywords. Syntax, compound sentence, connected compound sentence, compound sentence without connecting, segment, connected, load.

The syntax of the compound sentence is taught starting from the 2nd section of the 9th grade mother tongue textbook. This topic is considered a very difficult topic for schoolchildren to learn. Therefore, teaching this syntactic device to students requires good knowledge and skills from the teacher, in addition to the information given in the textbook. “The interpretation of compound sentences in our textbooks is very complicated. It is composed of two or more simple sentences based on content, grammatical form and tone. Its simple sentences are connected to each other by conjunctions, prepositions, auxiliaries, relative clauses, verb forms,

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and tone.”¹

In the topic “Simple and Compound Sentences” “An important sign for a sentence is the hyphen.” The number of clauses is the basis for dividing sentences into simple and compound sentences.² it is said. “It is impossible to thoroughly study the classification of compound sentences without instilling in the minds of the students the interpretation that the clause is the center of the sentence.”³

In this regard, “In terms of linguistic structure, the difference between a compound sentence and a simple sentence is clear to a certain extent. More precisely, if the part formed in a simple sentence is one, then in a compound sentence it is more than one, and it is formed by combining more than one simple sentences in terms of content and grammar.”⁴ A participle that is formed, that is, has participle forms (affirmation, negation, inclination, tense, person-number, meanings) expresses a separate sentence, can form the center of a specific sentence. Therefore, sentences with two or more formed clauses (but if the clauses in such sentences are not in the form of united clauses) are considered compound sentences. it is appropriate to quote his thoughts.⁵

For example: Our duty is to read - a simple sentence; Our duty is to study and research. In these sentences, all the meanings of participles are determined: confirmation, certainty (modal meaning), present tense, third person meanings, but they do not have material indicators. It is generally represented by a zero index. It is because of the presence of these meanings that it is considered a syntactic unit. But the statement that our task is to study and research is considered simple. Because “the sentence is a clause expressed by two or more noun units (words, phrases, phrases), and the means forming the clause are expressed only in the following clause and are related to all of them”, such a multi-clause sentence is considered a compound sentence.

At this point, the teacher is responsible for clarifying the issue. It is effective to use the FSMU method to solve the problem:

¹ B. To‘xliyev, M. Shamsiyeva, T. Ziyodova “O‘zbek tilini o‘qitish metodikasi” 2006. –B 163

² 9-sinf ona tili darsligi N. M. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov, A. Sh. Sobirov Toshkent- 2019. –B 17.

³ B. To‘xliyev, M. Shamsiyeva, T. Ziyodova “O‘zbek tilini o‘qitish metodikasi” 2006. –B 164.

⁴ R. Sayfullayeva, B. Mengliyev, G. Boqiyeva, M. Qurbonova, Z. Yunusova, M. Abuzalova “Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili” 2009. –B 391

⁵ N. Rasulova “Ona tilidan ma‘ruzalar” 2018. –B 126.

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Opinion - Sentences with two or more formed clauses (but if the clauses in such sentences are not in the form of united clauses) are considered compound sentences.

Reason - In these sentences, all the meanings of participles are determined in each participle: affirmation, certainty (modal meaning), time, person.

Example - Our task is to study and research.

General opinion - So, if the part formed in a simple sentence is one, then in a compound sentence it is more than one, and it is formed by combining more than one simple sentences in terms of content and grammar.

Regarding the use of conjunctions in conjunctions, the negative conjunction na..., na; simile -comparative conjunction as if, as if, like⁸; when explaining the topic of the conjunctions connected with the help of subtractive connective, it is necessary to mention that they are connective-loading.

The auxiliary na-na has been considered a negation conjunction as a type of equal conjunction. The linguist G. Abdurahmanov calls it a negation connector and shows that it also has the characteristic of predicate. In fact, this helper acts as both a binder and a downloader. When it acts as a connector, it gives the meaning of negation to some equal parts (components) and connects them: There is no meaning in his words, nor modesty in his actions. (O.). This auxiliary word acts as a predicate and appears in sentences with a negative content and shows a negative meaning: The chairman's son neither studies nor works anywhere.

The auxiliary “as” takes part in simple and compound sentences with the meaning of simile or comparison. In simple speech, it is closer to loading: Tursunoy seemed to accompany the song with his heart. (A. Mukh.). Something like a smile appeared on the old woman's face. (A. Kah.). As if the auxiliary in a compound sentence serves as one of the grammatical devices connecting the parts of a simple sentence, that is, in a compound sentence, unlike its function in a simple sentence, it is not only a predicate, but a linking predicate: Tomorrow will be a marriage , as if I were his wife. (Oyb.) He shouted so that the whole room seemed to shake. (A. Kah.)⁶

⁶ R. Sayfullayeva, B. Mengliyev, G. Boqiyeva, M. Qurbonova, Z. Yunusova, M. Abuzalova “Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili” 2009. –B 277.

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In addition, when the students are given the task of creating sentences using the word if, which serves to connect the parts of the connected sentence, most of the students write sentences like: If there is an event at our school, I will also participate they make It is necessary to explain that the parts of such sentences are considered as a conjunction with a subordinate clause. In this case, if the word if comes at the end of the first part, it is a subordinate clause, and if the word if comes after the compared clause in the structure of the second clause, then such a sentence is a dependent clause. it is necessary to mention that it is calculated.

The final “perception” part of the map is filled in by the students, a final decision is made and presented to the teacher. In order to further strengthen the acquired knowledge, the teacher will listen to the audio text for the students. The students distinguish the conjunctions connected by means of “if” and the adverbial clauses expressed by the participle “if”. In addition, performing resourcefulness exercises with students also gives effective results. Such exercises not only increase students' grammatical knowledge, but also their cognitive skills. For example, finding out which type of compound sentence the question of a logical test belongs to forms the student's grammatical knowledge, and choosing the correct option shows their creativity.

Formal syntax in the classification of compound sentences in many cases relies on their speech characteristics, external signs. Substantial syntax classification is based on the linguistic essence of the compound sentence. Therefore, when teaching topics about compound sentences, it is necessary to provide as much information as possible about all syntactic devices that can be used in the communicative speech process. For example, adverbs in speech: -b(-ib), -guncha (-kuncha, -kuncha), -gach (-kach, -kach); Compound sentences with -

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sa ham and -sa-da units are used a lot. Spring came and the days began to warm - the reason, the relationship of time; By the time my month comes, I have to finish all the work - time relation; Even if the sun rises, the day is cold - it would be appropriate if information such as the relationship of no obstacle is given in the textbook.

In short, it is the main task of the modern mother tongue teacher not only to memorize the rules, but also to form the ability to use these memorized rules in solving the problems encountered in everyday life. It should be one of the goals of the student to develop the manners of speaking meaningfully in his native language. When performing the tasks and exercises given in the textbook about the types of compound sentences, it is necessary to pay attention to the semantic features of any grammatical unit. If the student knows the semantic features of the linguistic unit he uses in his speech, any speech process becomes effective for him. After all, the main task of language education is not only to give students knowledge, but also to improve their language skills through this knowledge. As long as the acquired knowledge of the language does not become a skill, it will remain useless.

REFERENCES:

1. 9-sinf ona tili darsligi N. M. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov, A. Sh. Sobirov Toshkent- 2019. –B 17.
2. B. To‘xliyev, M. Shamsiyeva, T. Ziyodova “O‘zbek tilini o‘qitish metodikasi” 2006. –B 164.
3. R. Sayfullayeva, B. Mengliyev, G. Boqiyeva, M. Qurbonova, Z. Yunusova, M. Abuzalova “Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili” 2009. –B 391.
4. N. Rasulova “Ona tilidan ma’ruzalar” 2018. –B 126
5. 9-sinf ona tili darsligi N. M. Mahmudov, A. Nurmonov, A. Sh. Sobirov Toshkent- 2019. –B 71.